

BUILDING INFORMATION MODELLING (BIM) SKILLS FOR EMPLOYMENT IN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY IN RIVERS STATE

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Annotation:

The aim at assessing building information modelling skills for employment in construction industries in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought the following: Phase planning skills, 3D Coordination and Clash detection skills and Digital Fabrication skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State. Three objectives, research questions and hypotheses guided the study. This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The study was carried out in Rivers State. The population of the study was 80 respondents, comprising 20 architects and 60 construction site workers in Rivers State. The study was a census as the entire population was studied. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled "Building Information Modelling Questionnaire". The instrument contains five sections A-D. The instrument was structured on five-point Likert type rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). A corresponding numerical value of 5, 4,3,2 and 1 was assigned to the response scale for each item as represented below with real limits. The instrument was subjected to face-validation by three experts and the instrument has a reliability coefficient of 0.77. The findings of the study showed that the respondents agreed that phase planning skills are required for employment in construction industry in Rivers State. The findings of the study showed that the respondents agreed that 3D Coordination and Clash detection skills are required for employment in construction industry in Rivers State. The findings of the study showed that the respondents agreed that digital Fabrication skills are required for employment in construction industry in Rivers State. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendation were made: The practice of building information modelling skills amongst the students of building technology should be given consideration. Based on the results of this study it has clearly shown that building information modelling would improve students' performance in building technology. On-the-job training for lecturers in form of workshops should be organized on how to use building information modelling for better teaching of building technology to the students.

Keywords:

Building Information Modelling, Skills, Employment and Construction Industries.

INTRODUCTION

Building information modelling (BIM) is a digital representation of physical and functional attributes and characteristics of a facility. BIM is a knowledge resource for information about a facility forming a reliable basis for decisions during its life-cycle. Building information models (BIMs) are files (often, but not always in proprietary formats and containing proprietary data) which can be extracted, exchanged or networked to support decision-making regarding a building or another built asset (Abbas, et al.,2016). Current BIM software is used by individuals, businesses and government bodies who plan, design, construct, operate and sustain diverse physical infrastructures, such as wastewater, water, gas electricity, refuse and roads, bridges, ports, tunnels, among others. BIM brings together all of the information about every component of a building, in one place. It makes it possible for anyone to access that information for any purpose, for example, to integrate different aspects of the design more effectively. In this way, the risk of mistakes or discrepancies are reduced, and abortive costs minimized. Building information modelling (BIM) may result in many potential benefits to the construction industry (Abdul et al., 2017). To realize these benefits, the construction industry needs to cope with inevitable challenges related not only to the technology itself, but also to human resources. Research over the last decade indicates that individuals with adequate BIM skills may improve BIM implementation in construction projects. Conversely, people who lack BIM training and appropriate skills may hinder the advancement of BIM implementation in those projects. Research also suggests appropriate skill development of BIM may prepare students for career success and project success using phase planning skills, 3d coordination and clash detection skills, digital fabrication skills and digital layout skills.

Phase planning skills

The aim is to plan the site operations and the arrangements required in order for work to proceed as efficiently as possible during all stages of construction. The site plan is used to inform all parties of a construction project about internal and external logistic arrangements and the arrangements concerning work and safety. During the site planning phase there is a need to evaluate and plan things like site exclusion and separation, logistic arrangements, site limitations, dangers and protection, the number and location of office facilities and personnel rooms, working places and areas, site electrification and lightning, lifting arrangements and transportation, intermediate storage arrangements and logistic solutions for materials, firefighting and prevention of other special risks on site (Antón, et al., 2018). The site plan needs to be kept up to date. In practice the site plan can be made in a variety of ways. There are site plans made on town plan drawings with the use of a CAD program, plans that are drawn by hand or made with using sticker labels.

3D Coordination and Clash detection skills

The traditional design process involves overlapping designs on tracing paper to identify clashes, whereas, the computerized BIM process examines a large number of work-shared models at once. The process of BIM clash detection for architectural, structural, and MEP models integrating all design information into a master model is much easier and less time-consuming than the conventional method (Biolek, et al., 2019). When multi-trade models are combined into a single entity, architects, engineers, contractors, and designers use automatic processes of BIM to find and evaluate any instances of clashes in their model.

Digital Fabrication skills

The prefabrication method in the construction industry is a way to reduce the overall project schedule since the processes at the factory and the on-site fields are carried out simultaneously. This advantage can be obtained by simultaneously running a large number of processes on-site and at the factory, compared to the on-site process, in which all tasks are performed in order (Brumana, et al., 2020). This enables the contractor to actively utilize the prefabrication method for projects with an extremely short site schedule and complicated processes. Prefabrication also helps to reduce costs by preventing the waste of materials due to poor field processing and through the repeated training of workers. In addition, previous studies found that the use of prefabrication methodologies improved the quality of construction. Digital applications and IT technologies can significantly improve the quality of construction by accurately reflecting the initial design and entering this design in the fabrication equipment. In addition, prefabrication has the effect of reducing the wastage of resources by reducing the warehousing space, improving material quality, and optimizing the supply chain.

Digital fabrication refers to a methodology that systematically manages all processes, such as generation, design, material processing, and construction of a structure that is intended to be produced by utilizing digital tools. Digital fabrication technology is primarily used in specific projects, such as free-form buildings. In such projects, fabrication processes that exceed the conventional construction production methods are created through design goals and technical innovations (Bruno, & Roncella, 2019). The digital fabrication process of a construction project is generally classified as additional fabrication, and it is based on computer-based design methods and robotic-based production processes. In particular, for the construction of free-form parts, various members are processed and assembled through additional fabrication processes that utilize industrial robots. Owing to the recent development of digital technologies and the introduction of computer-based fabrication, buildings with very complex designs can also be realized which aids employment.

Employment

This term applies to an individual who is hired for a salary or compensation to initiate work or tasks for an organization. Although the employees can negotiate certain items in an employment agreement, the terms and conditions that are included and are mostly determined by the employer. Employment is an agreement between an employer and an employee that the employee will provide certain services. In return, the employee is paid a salary or hourly wage (Abduhu, et al., 2014). Although employees can negotiate certain items in an employment agreement, the terms and conditions are primarily determined by the employer especially in industries.

construction industry

Construction industry refers to the industrial branch of manufacturing and trade related to building, repairing, renovating, and maintaining infrastructures. Nigeria's construction sector offers several opportunities in commercial, residential, industrial, and infrastructure construction. The sector accommodates many foreign and local companies competing favourably for projects in the public and private sectors using appropriate skills.

Skill is noteworthy in everybody's life. Many technicians earn more than some school graduates because they acquire more practical skills than the theories unlike graduates who were sustained with theoretical encounters while in the universities. Skill acquisition is the ability to be prepared on a particular task or work and become expert in it. It is amazingly miserable that there is a huge rate of unemployment in various parts of the world especially in Nigeria. It is one reason for growth in wrongdoing in various places of the world. As of now, numerous graduates in the nation are as yet

jobless due to long system of education that is more theoretical than practical learning. It is substantial that Africa has the highest rate of jobless young people. The reason for high rate of unemployment amongst the vibrant youths in our society today is due to lack of skill to add up to what they learnt from their various institutions. In 2015, Nigeria have targeted to achieve one of the Millennium Development Goal (MDG) which is to eradicate extreme poverty and hunger by encouraging people who earn less than a dollar per day to engage in skill acquisition. Skill acquisition is a major tool for extreme poverty eradication and hunger with the aim of creating an avenue for jobs and wealth creation which will bring self-reliance and sufficiency and contributing to the growth and development of the economy in the country (Isaac, 2011). It is also important in the educational sector because it contributes to the improvement of human capital and employment in a nation. One of the goals of education is to gain appropriate skills and the development of mental, physical and social abilities and competencies for the people to live and add to the development of the society. There is a great need for skilled personnel in Nigeria today, who will be self-reliant and enterprising.

Statement of the Problem

There is a disturbing rate of youth joblessness in Nigeria. These young people made up of greater percentage level of Nigeria's economically active populace. College students are seen to be deficient in essential skills which incorporate; business enterprise abilities, interpersonal skills, teamwork skills, personal/executives' skills, computer/technical education skills, and administration/management abilities among others. They tend to build up the psychological area to the detriment of psychomotor domain and effective domain. In this manner we have students who are sound in information but lack capacity for making use of practical abilities to take care of issue.

All things considered, students are concerned more in retention of idea, this has made them to be found wanting in performing practical oriental jobs. Awogbenle and Iwuamadi (2010), discovered that Nigeria has a youth population of 80 million representing 60 percent of the overall population of the nation and 64 million of them are jobless, while 1.6 million are underemployed. This shows a lot of energies that would have been used to make livelihoods and improve the economy are being wasted. Since 1980's, the crucial roles of the youths have kept on enduring set back as they can barely engage in themselves in important work. The outcome is frustration expressed through different indecencies that constitute instability in the nation. The vices include extortion, arm robbery, kidnapping for ransom, internet fraud, prostitution and numerous other restiveness. This research will in general bring out various skills acquisition which can save the young people from joblessness and underemployment they found themselves and different government interventions that could help also. Against these backdrops, this study in this manner tried to assess building information modelling skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State.

Aim of the Study

The aim of the study is to asses building information modelling skills for employment in construction industries in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought the following:

1. Phase planning skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State.
2. 3D Coordination and Clash detection skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State.
3. Digital Fabrication skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State.
4. Digital layout skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What are the phase planning skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State?

2. What are the 3D Coordination and Clash detection skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State?
3. What are the digital Fabrication skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and were tested at .05 level of significance:

HO₁ There is no significant difference between the mean responses of Architects and other building experts on the phase planning skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State.

HO₂ There is no significant difference between the mean responses of Architects and other building experts on the 3D Coordination and Clash detection skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State.

HO₃ There is no significant difference between the mean responses of Architects and other building experts on the digital fabrication skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The descriptive survey research design is considered suitable because the study elicited data/information from respondents on building information modelling skills for employment in construction industries in Rivers State. Therefore, the design is relevant to the study since the sample of the students in technical colleges is selected to represent the population.

The population of the study was 80 respondents, comprising 20 architects and 60 construction site workers in Rivers State (field survey, 2023). The study was a census as the entire population was studied. This is in consonance with Maduabum (2007) who stated that, a survey in which the entire population is studied is referred to as census. The choice of census is due to the relatively small size of the population.

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled "Building Information Modelling Questionnaire". The instrument contains five sections A-D. The instrument was structured on five-point Likert type rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). A corresponding numerical value of 5, 4,3,2 and 1 was assigned to the response scale for each item as represented below with real limits.

The instrument was subjected to face-validation by three experts and the instrument has a reliability coefficient of 0.77. Data collected from the respondents were analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and t-test statistics were used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision for hypothesis was; if the calculated value of t (t-cal) is less than or equal to the critical value of (t-crit), accept the null hypothesis, otherwise rejected null hypothesis. The computation of the mean, standard deviation and t-test was carried out with statistical package for social sciences (SPSS).

Results

Research Question 1: What are the phase planning skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on phase planning skills for employment in construction industry

S/NO	Phase planning skills include:	Architects			Building Experts		
		X	SD	RMK	X	SD	RMK
1	Make a better understanding of the phasing schedule for stakeholders which shows the critical path of the project	3.57	.692	SA	3.81	1.039	A
2	Make a Dynamic phasing plans of occupancy offering multiple options and solutions to space conflicts on site	3.56	.732	SA	4.11	.859	A
3	Integrate planning of human, equipment and material resources with the BIM model to better schedule and cost estimate the project	4.28	.750	A	4.35	.719	A
4	Space and workspace conflicts identified and resolved ahead of the construction process	4.93	1.004	A	3.95	.932	A
5	Marketing purposes and publicity	4.16	.941	A	4.42	.844	A
6	Identification of schedule, sequencing or phasing issues	4.95	.875	A	4.09	.860	A
7	Make More readily constructible, operable and maintainable project	4.25	.931	A	4.32	.736	A
8	Monitor procurement status of project materials	4.99	1.088	A	4.31	.790	A
9	Increased productivity and decreased waste on job sites	4.05	.990	A	4.42	.625	A
	Grand Mean	4.30	0.89	A	4.19	0.82	A

Data in Table 1 revealed that Architects had a mean range of 3.56-4.99 and standard deviation range of 0.69 - 1.08. While the Building Experts had a mean range of 3.81-4.42 and standard deviation range of 0.62 - 1.03. The standard deviation shows the homogeneity of the respondents. The mean shows that the respondents agreed that phase planning skills are required for employment in construction industry in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: What are the 3D Coordination and Clash detection skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on 3D Coordination and Clash detection skills for employment in construction industry

S/NO	The 3D Coordination and Clash detection skills include:	Architects			Building Experts		
		X	SD	RMK	X	SD	RMK
1	Coordinate building project through a model	4.23	.834	A	4.07	.838	A
2	Reduce and eliminate field conflicts; which reduces RFI's significantly compared to other methods	4.40	.821	A	4.09	.808	A
3	Visualize construction	4.09	.722	A	4.04	.947	A
4	Increase productivity	4.18	.658	A	4.19	.766	A
5	Reduced construction cost; potentially less cost growth (i.e. less change orders)	4.05	.924	A	4.12	.982	A
6	Decrease construction time	4.19	.953	A	4.39	.774	A
7	Increase productivity on site	3.99	.881	A	4.19	.860	A
8	Be More accurate as built drawings	3.95	.990	A	4.26	.856	A
9	Use Design Authoring Software	3.98	1.03	A	4.32	.776	SA
	Grand Mean	4.12	0.87	A	4.19	0.85	A

Data in Table 2 revealed that Architects had a mean range of 3.15-4.40 and standard deviation range of 0.82 - 1.03. While the Building Experts had a mean range of 4.04-4.39 and standard deviation range of 0.76 - 0.94. The standard deviation shows the homogeneity of the respondents. The mean shows that the respondents agreed that 3D Coordination and Clash detection skills are required for employment in construction industry in Rivers State.

Research Question 3: What are the digital Fabrication skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on digital Fabrication skills for employment in construction industry

S/NO	Digital Fabrication skills include:	Architects			Building Experts		
		X	SD	RMK	X	SD	RMK
1	Adapt late changes in design	4.23	.881	A	4.34	.797	A
2	Reduced dependency on 2D paper drawings	4.44	.926	A	4.16	.902	A
3	Use Design Authoring Software	4.11	.858	A	3.70	1.059	A
4	Use Machine readable data for fabrication	4.26	.897	A	3.86	1.025	A
5	Use Fabrication methods	4.09	.989	A	4.17	.891	A
6	understand and create fabrication models	4.18	.889	A	4.25	.830	A
7	manipulate, navigate, and review a 3D model	3.97	.954	A	4.26	.809	A

8	extract digital information for fabrication from 3D models	4.04	1.017	A	4.32	.827	A
Grand Mean		4.17	0.93	A	4.13	0.89	A

Data in Table 3 revealed that Architects had a mean range of 3.97-4.44 and standard deviation range of 0.85 - 1.01. While the Building Experts had a mean range of 3.70-4.34 and standard deviation range of 0.79 - 1.05. The standard deviation shows the homogeneity of the respondents. The mean shows that the respondents agreed that digital Fabrication skills are required for employment in construction industry in Rivers State.

Hypotheses

HO₁ There is no significant difference between the mean responses of Architects and other building experts on the phase planning skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State.

Table 5: t-test Analysis on Phase Planning Skills Required of Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Graduates

Respondents	N	X	SD	α	d.f	t-Cal	t-Crit	RMK
Architects	20	4.30	.89	0.05	78	1.46	1.69	No Sig
Building Experts	60	4.19	.82					

Result in Table 4 revealed that t-cal (1.46) is less than t-crit (1.69) which indicates that the null hypothesis stated was accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of Architects and other building experts on the phase planning skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State.

HO₂ There is no significant difference between the mean responses of Architects and other building experts on the 3D Coordination and Clash detection skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State.

Table 5: t-test Analysis on 3D Coordination and Clash detection Skills Required of Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Graduates

Respondents	N	X	SD	α	d.f	t-Cal	t-Crit	RMK
Architects	20	4.12	.87	0.05	78	1.21	1.69	No Sig
Building Experts	60	4.19	.85					

Result in Table 5 revealed that t-cal (1.46) is less than t-crit (1.69) which indicates that the null hypothesis stated was accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of Architects and other building experts on the 3D Coordination and Clash detection skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State.

HO₃ There is no significant difference between the mean responses of Architects and other building experts on the digital fabrication skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State.

Table 6: t-test Analysis on digital fabrication Skills Required of Brick/Block Laying and Concreting Graduates

Respondents	N	X̄	SD	A	d.f	t-Cal	t-Crit	RMK
Architects	20	4.17	.93	0.05	78	1.23	1.69	No Sig
Building Experts	60	4.13	.89					

Result in Table 6 revealed that t-cal (1.46) is less than t-crit (1.69) which indicates that the null hypothesis stated was accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of Architects and other building experts on the digital fabrication skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study showed that the respondents agreed that phase planning skills are required for employment in construction industry in Rivers State. The hypothesis in Table 4 revealed that t-cal (1.46) is less than t-crit (1.69) which indicates that the null hypothesis stated was accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of Architects and other building experts on the phase planning skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State. The findings of the study is in agreement with Abanda et al., (2015), who highlighted the use of BIM to manage project information management in construction projects and stressed that the adoption of BIM in the construction industry has helped bring solutions to the sector's problems. Antón, et al. (2018) explained that dated the utilization of Information Technology (IT) in the United Kingdom to early 1970s and further opined that the globalization of construction works such as the pre-fabrication and assembly of building components will greatly increase the usefulness of IT in construction projects. The prediction of Ba Chacón, et al., (2021), is a current reality in the construction industry as evidenced in some construction projects. Moreover, argued that for the construction industry to thrive and be competitive, it needs to be innovative and improve the ways, methods, and techniques of delivering its products.

The findings of the study showed that the respondents agreed that 3D Coordination and Clash detection skills are required for employment in construction industry in Rivers State. The hypothesis in Table 5 revealed that t-cal (1.46) is less than t-crit (1.69) which indicates that the null hypothesis stated was accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of Architects and other building experts on the 3D Coordination and Clash detection skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State. The findings of the study is in line with Be Casazza, et al., (2019) noted that the development of BIM framework is significant in the overall process of integrating BIM in construction process to improve the various project activities and processes. It is hoped that the development of the study's BIM-module for Building technology will further help to bridge the gap in both knowledge and practice, and enhance the capacity of project teams to gauge the level of BIM adoption for construction and information management process in construction projects.

The findings of the study showed that the respondents agreed that digital Fabrication skills are required for employment in construction industry in Rivers State. The hypothesis in Table 6 revealed that t-cal (1.46) is less than t-crit (1.69) which indicates that the null hypothesis stated was accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of Architects and other building experts on the digital fabrication skills for employment in construction industry in Rivers State. The findings

of the study is in line with Davidson, et al., (2020) who depicted BIM as a “global digital technology” with the capacity to ease the construction process, facilitate coordination and enhance the efficient delivery of project information. Also, Depecke, et al., (2021) described BIM as an “innovative technology” which can support project activities throughout the project lifecycle. More so, Faltýnová, et al., (2016) noted that BIM had transformed the construction industry in such a way that construction stakeholders have developed an interest in its implementation for their diverse job nature, advocated that BIM provide “single, non-redundant, interoperable information repository” capable of supporting every stage, process and functional units in a construction project.

Conclusion

The study, it is therefore, concluded that the Building Information modelling skills are required for employment in industries. The industry demands for BIM knowledgeable graduates are increasing rapidly and becoming more complex. For architects to remain employable and relevant in the industry, they need to recognise and key into the required core competencies of the construction industry. This study obtained secondary data from the meta-analysis of the literature, which core BIM competencies. These were further subjected to targeted respondents to elicit primary data.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendation were made:

1. The practice of building information modelling skills amongst the students of building technology should be given consideration. Based on the results of this study it has clearly shown that building information modelling would improve students’ performance in building technology.
2. On-the-job training for lecturers in form of workshops should be organized on how to use building information modelling for better teaching of building technology to the students.
3. There should be adequate provisions of facilities, tools and equipment, which are necessary for teaching concept and skills in building information modelling effectively.

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